

Data Science and Machine Learning for hurricane forecasting

Stefan Schmainta

2010837145@stud.fh-kufstein.ac.at

Data Science & Intelligent Analytics

FH Kufstein, Tirol, Austria

January 5, 2022

Abstract

This paper demonstrates the importance of Data Science techniques within the Natural Sciences sector, more specifically, within the area of climate research such as global warming and hurricane development. During times of a continued increase in global temperatures, it more important than ever to further improve today's forecasting and prediction methods. Two possible Data Science approaches are being demonstrated and proven to add value to the traditional statistics based forecasting methods.

1 Introduction

Data Science has found its way into different areas, improving, enhancing and sometimes even replacing various existing forecasting methods. When it comes to weather forecasting or extreme weather forecasting, things are even more challenging. Physicists define climate as a “complex system”. While there are a lot of interpretations about it, in this specific case we can consider “complex” to be “unsolvable in analytical ways”. Is it even possible to collect data that is somewhere in the atmosphere and create some generalized model of it? This paper should generate some insights, that there are Data Science methods available, that can be beneficial with weather forecasting.

called a tropical disturbance. As the warm air causes water to evaporate, it creates lift in the low pressure area. The rising warm, moist air releases energy as it cools and condenses into rain clouds. The process continues building energy in the rain clouds which can erupt into a violent storm encompassing hundreds of square miles. As the winds begin to rotate over the warm water, energy continues to build, eventually creating a hurricane, typhoon, or tropical cyclone. Throughout this paper, the term “hurricane” will be used².

2 Background

Hurricanes, typhoons, and tropical cyclones are severe tropical storms. Although these storms share common characteristics in formation and impact, the term used is determined by wind speed and location. These storms form over warm water and draw energy from the evaporation of water as they pass over the ocean surface. The storms begin simply as an area of low pressure and thunderstorms

Figure 1: Simplified graphic of the inside of a hurricane by the National Oceanic & Atmospheric Administration. (<https://scijinks.gov/hurricane/>).

When the maximum sustained winds of a storm reaches 74 mph it is by definition a hurricane⁸. After reaching even higher wind speeds, the hurricane will be classified into 5 different categories based on the Saffir-Simpson Hurricane Wind Scale⁷:

- **Category One:**
74-95 mph or 119-153 km/h.
- **Category Two:**
96-110 mph or 154-177 km/h
- **Category Three:**
111-129 mph or 178-208 km/ h.
- **Category Four:**
130-156 mph or 209-251 km/h.
- **Category Five:**
156 mph or higher or 251 km/h or higher.

As the global temperature level continues to rise⁵, it is anticipated that the frequency and intensity of natural disasters will increase as well. Therefore, it must be evaluated, if modern forecasting techniques can be improved or enhanced by applying state-of-the-art Data Science methods.

3 Forecasting methods

This section will take a closer look at some available methods and algorithms that could be applied for climate predictions and where Data Science techniques can bring added value.

Data Science and Machine Learning

While there are many data science methods out there, certainly not every one is suitable for hurricane predictions or climate forecasting. To get a better understanding, let's briefly elaborate the term "data science" and take closer look into possible hurricane forecasting methods.

The simplest definition of data science is "the extraction of actionable insights from raw data".

With that being said, data science consists of different skills like Data Analysis, Data Mining, Statistical Learning, Knowledge Discovery, Pattern Discovery, Big Data and more. Although these terms are all single areas for themselves, within the data science, they all fall under the same umbrella which is learning from data³.

Machine Learning is a branch of data science that broadly aims to enable computers to "learn" without being directly programmed. It has origins in the artificial intelligence movement of the 1950s and emphasizes practical objectives and applications, particularly prediction and optimization. Computers "learn" in machine learning by improving their performance at tasks through "experience". In practice, "experience" usually means fitting to data. Although, there is not always a clear boundary between machine learning and statistical approaches, many machine learning algorithms are based on statistical methods¹.

3.1 Multilayer perceptron (MLP)

A Multilayer perceptron, or MLP, refers to a deep learning (DL) model that has multiple feed-forward and fully connected hidden layers between an input layer and an output layer. Each hidden layer computes a linear combination of the outputs from the previous layer and applies a nonlinear activation function. Thus, each layer transforms its input data into a slightly more abstract and composite representation, making it possible for MLP to learn

highly complex and nonlinear relationships involving many predictors. MLP can be used for both classification and regression⁹.

An experiment, which was operationally supported by the Deep Science Agile Initiative at Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL), has been conducted in order to prove the significance of an MLP when predicting the intensity level of a hurricane.

Figure 2: The 24-h intensity change of the Mean of Absolute value of Errors (MAE) from MLP and preexisting statistical models. (<https://doi.org/10.1175/WAF-D-20-0104.1>).

The MLP has not only demonstrated competitive predictive skills, but also maintained relatively high level of independence from other operational models due to its DL-based modeling framework. As a result, the MLP would potentially be a meaningful addition to the methods used by the National Hurricane Center to further improve official forecasting skills.

While MLP has proven to add value to current prediction methods, it still is far from being perfect. Especially when talking about hurricane intensity predictions, the error-margin is very small. When a predicted category 2 hurricane turns into a category 4, the consequences could be devastating. Therefore, research efforts for hurricane intensity predictions needs to continue and keep improving.

3.2 Ensemble learning

Classification is a widely used term when talking about data science or machine learning, where "classification" is just the broad overview of different classification algorithms. Possible algorithms which could be used for classification are for exam-

ple Logistic Regression, Naive Bayes classifier, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Decision Trees or Support Vector Machines (SVM). But instead of using a single classifier, it is also possible to combine the outputs of several classification methods, in an attempt to reach a more accurate and reliable solution. In this case we talk about ensemble learning.

Figure 3: Combining classifiers with different decision boundaries reduce error. (http://scholarpedia.org/article/File:Combining_classifiers2.jpg).

In a study, the researchers used machine learning to remove certain groups of hurricane predictions from ensembles — sets of predictions from weather models that are based on a range of weather possibilities — to lower errors and improve forecasts four to six days ahead. Although these models are good and getting better, they are far from perfect. Each prediction may account for a slight variation in the many variables that make up weather, such as energy from the ocean and clouds⁴.

Figure 4: Example of 144-h clustering using forecasts of Tropical Storm Soulik initialized at 0000 UTC 16 Aug 2018. The (a) 129 ensemble tracks are assigned to clusters with (b) central polynomial trajectories shown. Ensemble tracks are (c) color-coded by cluster with (d) cluster-mean tracks shown. The observed track of Soulik in (d) is shown in black. Markers in (d) indicate Soulik’s position at 96, 120, and 144 h.. (http://scholarpedia.org/article/File:Combining_classifiers2.jpg).

However, clustering may help forecasters better predict the variety of scenarios in different locations along the storm’s path and get more precise warnings to people who may be unaware of the changing weather situation⁶.

4 Conclusion

While climate forecasting and especially hurricane predictions are extremely difficult due to all the different factors that can impact the behavior of a hurricane, adding a data science view to the meteorologist’s analysis, can still add great value. The key is to understand which methods are available and more specifically, to identify which data science approach is best used for a certain scenario. As we continuously generate more data through new sensors and observations, it is definitely recommended to make use of the data and to further improve ex-

isting forecasting methods.

References

- [1] Qifang Bi, Katherine E Goodman, Joshua Kaminsky, and Justin Lessler. What is machine learning? a primer for the epidemiologist. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aje/kwz189>, 2019.
- [2] Julie Ann P. Casani Bruce W. Clements. Disasters and public health (second edition). <https://www.sciencedirect.com/book/9780128019801/disasters-and-public-health>, 2016.
- [3] Chitra G Desai. Conference fdp - implementation of t y b.sc (computer science) syllabus cbcs pattern 2019. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17701.22240>, 2021.
- [4] Penn State Institute for Computational and Data Sciences. Application of machine learning can optimize hurricane track forecast. <https://www.newswise.com/articles/application-of-machine-learning-can-optimize-hurricane-track-forecast>, 2020.
- [5] NOAA National Centers for Environmental Information. State of the climate: Global climate report for annual 2020. <https://www.ncdc.noaa.gov/sotc/global/202013>, 2021.
- [6] Alex M. Kowaleski and Jenni L. Evans. Use of multiensemble track clustering to inform medium-range tropical cyclone forecasts. <https://doi.org/10.1175/WAF-D-20-0003.1>, 2020.
- [7] National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration. The saffir-simpson hurricane wind scale. <https://www.nhc.noaa.gov/pdf/sshws.pdf>.
- [8] National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration. What is a hurricane? <https://oceanservice.noaa.gov/facts/hurricane.html>.
- [9] Wenwei Xu, Karthik Balaguru, Andrew August, Nicholas Lalo, Nathan Hodas, Mark DeMaria, and David Judi. Deep learning experiments for tropical cyclone intensity forecasts. 2021.